

Revolution

continues...

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From the Editorial Director

Counting Confusion: Bangladesh's missing headcounts equal to Sri Lanka's entire population

By Julfekar Dehan

Photo: Collected

Numbers can significantly influence a country's growth and development, and can also impact its GDP per capita. Bangladesh, the eighth-most populous country in the world, is familiar with large numbers of its remittances and exports. But few figures carry as much weight as the size of the population.

Two of the country's most important institutions, the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS) and the Election Commission (EC), are painting two entirely different pictures. The BBS's Population and Housing Census 2022 put the country's population at 16.98 crore. Yet the EC declared it to be 19 crore.

That gap of more than two crore is almost equal to the entire population of Sri Lanka. This raises a fundamental question, has the population grown by two crore in just two to three years, or were these people overlooked in the census?

BBS vs EC

"We prepared the voter list by visiting households, and that's how we got the information. This is the accurate data. Our total population is 19 crore, of which 1.51 crore are living abroad. In Dhaka city alone, there are 1.51 crore people," said Election Commissioner Tahmida Ahmad at a recent dialogue with civil society representatives.

Tahmida has termed the data provided by BBS on the country's population as "questionable".

"At first, they [BBS] published one figure, and later it was said to reduce it,"

In contrast, the BBS insists its first-ever digital census in the country's history was more accurate. The Post Enumeration Check conducted by the Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies (BIDS) even reported the lowest-ever net coverage error of 2.75%, according to the statistics bureau. 'Where did they find 19 crore?'

Asked about the EC's figure, Md Mahmuduzzaman, director of the BBS Census Wing, said, "We reported what we found through the census. Where did they find 19 crore?" Responding to the EC's claim that their method was more accurate because it involved house-to-house visits, he said, "Then they should run the bureau of statistics."

He added, "What kind of methodology they followed, only they know. We went door to door and counted every man. We visited every household, collected data on household population, names, educational qualifications, everything." Mahmuduzzaman went further, suggesting duplication might explain the EC's higher figure.

"What they are bringing, only they know. Maybe they are counting people who live elsewhere too. For example, a member of a household may live in a Dhaka University hall. They might have been counted at home once, and again at the university. If that's the case, then why stop at 19 crore? It could be 31 crore."

"Our data is more accurate. We followed the modified de facto method, collecting data door to door from every household." On expatriates, he clarified that the BBS did not count those living abroad. So is this the gap of not counting the people living abroad? If so, why did BBS first publish one figure, and later reduce it, as the EC claimed?

The real problem

While neither the BBS nor the EC has explained the gap, in Bangladesh's polarised landscape, numbers are rarely just numbers. Population data underpins nearly every sectoral plan from education and healthcare to infrastructure and employment.

They determine how many schools and hospitals we build, how much food we import, how we plan infrastructure, and even how we negotiate aid and loans. Take GDP per capita, for example. A difference of two crore people could shift a country's global ranking in terms of population and economic progress.

From the health perspective, per capita expenditure could be distorted. In education, the planning of classrooms, teacher recruitment, and budgets becomes vulnerable when the denominator itself is uncertain. Behind the debate between two government agencies lies a deeper problem, the public is being denied clear, reliable information, which is a serious problem and not uncommon in Bangladesh.

Salad's silent revolution: Nanotech from field to fork

*Sumaiya Hassan . Research Assistant and Lab-in-Charge
Bionanotechnology and Nanomedicine Lab of Islamic University*

Illustration: Mahdi/Econology/

Behind every flawlessly fresh, premium-grade, perfectly crisp lettuce, or vibrant tomato on your plate lies a years-long silent revolution that is reshaping our agriculture and food industry.

Food waste and hunger have always been a burning question, exacerbated by environmental pollution. FAO, in a statistics, revealed that about one-third of the food annually went to waste globally and most of it spoiled before it even reached the consumer and don't forget about pest outbreaks and climate stress that assist in lowering the yields and yield quality. Scientists' predictions warn us that we will need to feed 10 billion people

by 2050 with hotter, less arable land, and increasingly unpredictable weather patterns, seemingly inappropriate to grow most of the harvest.

But here comes the twist, we don't need to worry about producing more food for the huge number of predicted mouths, we already produce enough, which somehow becomes a waste before it reaches your plate. So the solution isn't just growing more food—it's getting smarter about every atom of what we already grow. And here comes the revolutionary invention, "Nanotechnology" which is quietly rewriting the rules of agriculture, one molecule at a time.

Uncertainty to data-driven harvesting

If anyone says farming we used to unconsciously imagine the scenario of a poor farmer working his best to grow more with bare minimum tools while placing his hopes entirely on favourable weather for a decent harvest. If he is lucky he will get some good harvest but most of the time he is not. Fast forward to today's age, we have outgrown from complete luck to precision agriculture, where nanotechnology has made

it possible to measure, control, and monitor growing conditions precisely at the molecular level which would have seemed a sci-fi movie plot just a generation ago. In simple terms precision agriculture means using just the right amount of everything you need to grow anything like the exact amount of water, or pesticides you need for your cilantro to grow properly.

Surprisingly the service does not stop there, from measuring soil moisture to plant stress nano-based precision agriculture has made once a physically and emotionally drenching farming into an almost automated and passive activity.

Anything you possibly can imagine a farmer needs to do in his field like analysing seed quality, type, and amount of pesticides that should be used, and weather monitoring, all has become automated and one can optimise the required factor according to the preference. Thanks to the blessings of nanotechnology, we are now witnessing the transformation of traditional farming into a high-tech ecosystem. What makes precision agriculture unique is that rather than human dependency, it has its own

sensing (nanosensor), communicating (IoT), and thinking device (AI) installed in it. For example, for an ecosystem to function properly it's mandatory to have everything be systematically interconnected, much like how a human body relies on a well-coordinated nervous system that commands and monitors our limbs and organs, ensuring each performs its designated role.

The Internet of Things or IoT is like that nervous system interconnecting necessary sensors or equipment where nanotechnology makes them ultra-sensitive, and miniaturised size for higher efficiency. Artificial intelligence or AI is like the human brain that converts this nanosensor and IoT data into actionable intelligence through machine learning and predictive analytics. This brain of smart farming can accurately forecast weather, diseases, and yields, while computer vision detects pests and stress early to enable precise, timely interventions that can cut chemical use by up to 90%.

The entire workflow is simpler than it appears: initially, micro nano-sensors are placed within the soil to accurately track nutrient qualities or temperature with exceptional accuracy. Subsequently, through integration with an IoT network, this information is transmitted wirelessly to a centralised control system or directly to the farmer's mobile device, enabling targeted irrigation, fertilisation, and pest management strategies with the help of AI. The real-world examples are nano soil sensor-based IoT systems in India which significantly reduce agricultural

What makes precision agriculture unique is that rather than human dependency, it has its own sensing (nanosensor), communicating (IoT), and thinking device (AI)...

water waste during dry periods through optimized irrigation. Farmers in the wine regions in California use nanosensors to track the climate conditions at the micro level surrounding grape plants to always remain alert about any heat or water-related stress the plants are going well before any visible signs of damage appear. The 'farming with bare minimum tools' past has advanced into 'bare minimum effort farming' as the fusion of nanotech, IoT, and AI has become a powerful tool kit for precision maintenance and surveillance.

The miracle of nanotechnology has not finished yet. Other than instrumental improvement, nanoparticles are also rewriting the history of biological sciences. Nano-based fertilisers have already made headlines for their high efficacy. For instance, researchers at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University in India developed zinc oxide nanoparticle-based fertilisers that show up to 70% higher absorption rates in crops like maize, reducing excess runoff and minimising environmental pollution compared to conventional fertilisers.

Nano-fertilisers and pesticides, such as silica nanoparticles, are being explored to protect rice crops from fungal infections, offering longer-lasting protection with fewer chemical applications. Nano-coated seeds, such as those developed by ICAR in India, improve germination rates and drought resistance. The issue of sustainability has also been addressed by nano agriculture as this practice could reduce global fertiliser waste significantly, enhancing sustainability, food security, and crop productivity, particularly in regions vulnerable to climate change and resource scarcity. Smart farming slashes fertiliser use by up to 40% and chemical pesticide use by 50–80%, helping to lower emissions and runoff. In drought-hit regions, precision

irrigation systems save 20–40% of water. Soil nanosensors developed by researchers at MIT also track carbon sequestration, supporting climate goals. Economically, smart farming yields 15–25% ROI, increases U.S. productivity by \$20 billion, and saves \$15 billion in environmental costs.

Making traditional packaging smart

In traditional agriculture, even if the farmer is able to make a decent amount of yield, half of it is used to become waste in transportation and storage. Scientists have also found the solution to this problem in nanotechnology. Just like smart farming, smart packaging is also a new yet trendy concept among researchers and policymakers. Smart packaging or smart bio packaging can be simply defined as packages that can monitor and protect the food inside it and alert the customer about its freshness. Now the question is doesn't the expiry date play mostly the same role? Here is the answer: when it's about the food safety measurement, numbers become invalid. Let me explain- manufacturers usually set the expiration date based on their peak freshness.

If the parameter is a triangle that starts with manufacturing, the expiration date will be the peak of the triangle, not the third point or end point of the triangle. So it means that maybe when you are throwing away your favourite juice, it doesn't mean the food has spoiled. Additionally, food shelf life and storage conditions are proportional. For example, food like yoghurt, if stored in cold and sealed conditions, can remain fresh for months, even beyond the expiry date but if it's in the opposite condition, it will spoil before the date. One of the most dangerous factors is microbial contamination, which can be done simply by mishandling and the scary part is for some food you may not notice as they may look or smell fine. So the

one and only solution is a package telling us whether the food inside it is good to consume or not. Smart bio packaging is the integration of active and smart packaging. Active packaging interacts with the food itself and improves the shelf life. The characteristics include incorporating silver or zinc oxide-based antimicrobial agents to kill microbes, ethylene absorbers like Bluapple or FreshPaper that delay ripening, and pH-sensitive dyes that change color with spoilage (such as the color-changing tags developed by MIT). In active packaging, nanoparticles are used to enhance the efficiency of the active ingredients.

The role of smart packaging is to monitor the overall condition of the product and provide the information about freshness, or spoilage of the product to the customer. Usually, they have a nanosensor attached to them that regulates and monitors the quality and inway the outcome. Unlike traditional plastics, these packaging solutions are made from renewable sources such as seaweed, mushroom, starch, and chitosan that not only decompose naturally but also support circular economies by utilising agricultural waste.

Bangladesh's position in this revolution

Bangladesh has emerged as a promising player in the field of nano-based smart agriculture, leveraging scientific innovation and institutional support to modernise its farming practices. Prof. Dr. Md. Zaved Hossain Khan from Jashore University of Science and Technology (JUST), has already made headlines with the invention of nano urea fertiliser which is already being hailed as a game-changer. This tiny miracle drastically reduces fertiliser use while boosting crop productivity — a breakthrough so powerful it's now patented and being validated in

international trials. The momentum doesn't stop there. With the backing of institutions like the Krishi Gobeshona Foundation (KGF), Bangladesh has expanded its research into nano-pesticides, nano-sensors, nano-minerals, and biogenic nanoparticles, integrating these advancements into crop, livestock, and aquaculture systems. Ongoing field trials and real-time monitoring through nano-sensors reflect the integration of precision farming practices, while nano-based soil conditioners and filtration systems address challenges related to salinity, degradation, and water management. These innovations position Bangladesh as a forward-moving nation in South Asia's agricultural transformation, with nanotechnology at the core of its strategy to ensure food security, environmental sustainability, and technological resilience. Another promising contribution comes from Dr ATM Mijanur Rahman at Islamic University, who is pioneering the development of green silver nanoparticle-based nanofungicides. His optimised formulation offers an eco-friendly and highly effective solution to Bakanae disease, a serious threat to rice cultivation in Bangladesh. In addition to fungicides, Dr Rahman is also advancing research in green nanoparticle-based biopackaging and biosensors, adding further dimensions to Bangladesh's nano-agricultural capabilities.

So, what's really in your salad? The answer is: A nano revolution.

About the writer:

Sumaiya Hassan is a research assistant and Lab-in-charge at the Bionanotechnology and Nanomedicine Lab at Islamic University, Bangladesh. Her work focuses on harnessing nanotechnology for sustainable agriculture, developing functional foods, and exploring the role of microorganisms in promoting health and environmental balance. She can be reached at:

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/sumaiyahassannano/>

Climate Colonialism: History of Injustice

By Raisa Shakera Nishat

In South Asia, millions today suffer from Type 2 diabetes, a disease often framed as a lifestyle disease. But studies suggest a deeper, more disturbing origin. Studies link this metabolic disorder to epigenetic changes inherited from ancestors who endured colonial famines. During British colonial rule, exploitative economic policies and forced grain exports led to devastating food shortages across the Indian subcontinent and beyond.

These were not natural disasters, but politically manufactured catastrophes. Millions died, while food exports continued, and local resilience was eroded. Malnourished mothers bore children

with altered metabolic profiles, primed to store fat in anticipation of scarcity. That survival mechanism, passed down through generations, is now contributing to a modern-day health crisis--diabetes. In effect, trauma was passed down—not just socially, but biologically.

This is not just about famine. It's about how global injustices are embedded in biology. It reveals how vulnerability is socially and historically constructed, and how the legacies of empire, racism, and global inequality are not only embedded in our institutions, but potentially, in our genes. Fast forward to the climate crisis, and we observe a disturbingly similar

pattern. Rising sea levels, salinity intrusion, extreme weather events and food insecurity resulting from CC disproportionately affect small states and fragile economies, many of which had little role in creating the problem. The emissions that drive this crisis largely originate from the developed economies, but the consequences fall hardest on low-lying nations and economically marginalised populations.

Now, Climate change is described as a shared global challenge, but as we see, its consequences are distributed mostly along colonial fault lines. This phenomenon has a name- “climate colonialism”, where the carbon-intensive wealth of some is built at the cost of the ecological vulnerability of others. But climate colonialism doesn’t just shape economics and infrastructure. It may also be reshaping the biological futures of vulnerable populations.

One of the numerous modern-day examples can be Cancer Alley, an 85-mile stretch along the Mississippi River in Louisiana, USA. This region, being home primarily to populations of colour and low-income communities, is crowded with petrochemical plants, refineries, and industrial polluters.

The term “Cancer Alley” is not metaphorical; but ironic. The name owes to the fact that residents of the region suffer from abnormally high rates of cancer, respiratory illness, and birth defects. What they experience is a textbook case of environmental racism,

where toxic infrastructure is deliberately placed near communities with the least power to resist. But the effects go even deeper than we once thought. Studies now point to toxin-induced genetic damage, epigenetic silencing of tumour-suppressor genes, and biological legacy effects that may span generations. This means environmental hazards don’t just harm today’s children—they could be scripting the health outcomes of their grandchildren. Much like the famine-diabetes link in South Asia, the pollution-chronic diseases-cancer triad in places like Cancer Alley suggests a long-term genetic imprint of structural injustice.

Just as famine trauma altered the epigenome of colonial subjects, climate and pollution trauma is scripting new biological legacies today.

This raises ethical questions. When one gets diagnosed with high blood pressure or diabetes, we blame their diet or lack of exercise or other behavioural choices. But what if the air they breathe has carcinogens? What if they live in urban heat islands with no safe space to walk, or their water contains traces of lead and nitrates?

When structural conditions constrain choices, blaming individuals becomes not only inaccurate but unethical. The problem is not personal failure—it is policy failure, historical violence, and ongoing structural neglect. This demands a radical shift in how we understand public health, sustainability, and development. Climate action must go beyond decarbonization;

it must include reparative justice. That means recognising not only who is harmed,

It demands that we confront the bio-social consequences of colonialism, racism, and predatory capitalism.

but also why, and what historical forces positioned them there. Climate change is often treated as a technical issue, solvable with renewables and market mechanisms. But it is also a story of compounded injustice. It demands that we confront the bio-social consequences of colonialism, racism, and predatory capitalism. It calls for reparative frameworks—not only through climate finance or adaptation funding—but through redefining global health, resilience, and responsibility.

Climate change is not the great equaliser. It is the great revealer. And what it reveals is a world where the wounds of colonialism and racialised capitalism are still open, and in some cases, are becoming part of our very DNA. It shows us who has been left behind, who continues to be sacrificed, and who must finally be held accountable—not just for carbon emissions, but for the invisible genetic scars they leave behind.

About the author

Raisa Shakera Nishat is an Environmentalist living in Melbourne, Australia. She can be reached at: nishat0309@gmail.com

From Likes to Uprising

How Nepal's social media ban sparked a revolution | *A behavioural economics comedy of errors*

Naomi Rahman

A protestor with police vest and riot shield snatched from the police. Photo: AP

On 19 July 2024, Bangladesh plunged into a nationwide blackout branded as a “digital crackdown.” Barely a year later, in September 2025, Nepal decided to follow an even bolder script: banning social media platforms at once, from Facebook to Twitter to WhatsApp.

The outcome was anything but orderly. By 8 September, thousands of citizens—many in uniform—marched from Maitighar to Parliament, waving the national flag and shouting in unison. Within days, the unimaginable had happened: Nepal's prime ministers were forced out of office.

The drama did not erupt overnight. The roots of the anger went deeper than an app ban. For years, corruption scandals had smouldered

beneath the surface, preparing the ground for an explosion. Among them was the notorious Airbus deal, where the purchase of two A330 jets caused a staggering loss of NPR 1.47 billion. Accountability crawled forward at a snail's pace, and frustration mounted.

The steady parade of political dynasties, the entrenchment of nepotistic perks, and the absence of real accountability meant the youth were already primed for fury. Intellectuals had repeatedly warned of these cracks in governance, but their cautions went unheeded.

Warnings also came when the government contemplated restrictions on digital space. Nara Bahadur Thapa, a former executive at

Nepal's Central Bank, cautioned that social media bans could harm Nepal's investment climate and even weaken its sovereign credit rating at a time when the nation was preparing to graduate from Least Developed Country status.

Digital rights advocate Santosh Sigdel similarly argued that such measures would degrade Nepal's governance ranking and trample on the constitutional right to information.

At first glance, the story seemed like one of a country furious about losing its online lifeline. But beneath the outrage, the heart of the matter was corruption, billion-rupee scandals, entitlement, and broken governance. The social media ban merely provided the spark that lit a fire already waiting to burn.

Behavioural economics offers a lens to make sense of why a ban on apps turned into a revolution. Daniel Kahneman, the Nobel-winning psychologist, famously argued that "losses loom larger than gains."

This principle of loss aversion helps explain why people react more strongly to losing something than to gaining something new. For Nepali youth, the sudden disappearance of Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram was not a minor inconvenience.

A Pew Research study in 2023 found that 82% of Nepali youth under 30 used at least one social media platform every day. Cutting them off was not simply about disabling apps; it meant stripping away their social connection, their source of news, their work opportunities, and even part of their identities. The framing effect also played a role. The government packaged the ban as a "national security" measure, rather than what

critics saw as a clear attempt at censorship. Cass Sunstein, in his work on nudges, shows how framing can determine compliance: people tend to accept restrictions when they are wrapped in patriotic language.

But in Nepal, the frame was too thin. Citizens saw through it immediately, hearing only the echoes of censorship. Another powerful bias was the bandwagon effect. Once a few bold individuals took to the streets, others followed in their footsteps. Psychologists describe this as social proof: when uncertain, people copy others' actions.

Malcolm Gladwell popularised this as the "tipping point," where small sparks ignite massive flames. In Kathmandu, a single protest selfie shared on alternative apps like Signal or Telegram spread faster than the government could block servers.

At the same time, the government itself fell prey to overconfidence bias. Kahneman has shown that people systematically overestimate their control over events. Nepal's leaders assumed they could ban 26 platforms overnight and that citizens would simply accept the decision. Instead, they triggered a digital generation clash: a connected youth against an out-of-touch ruling class.

This story was not unique to Nepal. The region has witnessed similar upheavals. Sri Lanka's Aragalaya movement in 2022 forced President Gotabaya Rajapaksa to resign after months of protests against corruption, inflation, and fuel shortages. Protesters organised almost entirely through Facebook and Twitter until the government attempted, unsuccessfully, to block them. As economist Amartya Sen once argued, no famine has ever occurred in a functioning democracy; by extension, no government can expect peace while cutting off the digital

oxygen of its people. In Indonesia, August 2025 also saw citizens pour into the streets over economic grievances. Further afield, Iran's 2022 decision to ban WhatsApp and Instagram during the Mahsa Amini protests had the opposite effect of what was intended: VPN downloads surged by 3,000% within a week.

The more states tried to lock the digital gates, the more determined citizens became to break through. Richard Thaler once quipped that people are not dumb, the world is simply hard. Young people, in particular, always find a way around digital walls, whether through VPNs, proxies, or encrypted apps.

Statistics only underscore the inevitability of Nepal's unrest. Internet penetration in the country stands at over 44%, with youth making up 60% of daily social media users.

Youth unemployment hovers at 19%, according to the World Bank. On Transparency International's Corruption Perceptions Index in 2024, Nepal scored just 34 out of 100, ranking 108th worldwide. The trust deficit is glaring: 70% of Nepalis believe their government is corrupt. Put all of these together—high unemployment, corruption, and a sudden clampdown on digital expression—and silence was never an option. The natural result was storming crowds.

In the end, behavioural economics offers governments a set of warning labels. Loss aversion explains why people resist when freedoms are taken away. The framing effect shows that calling censorship "security" convinces no one. The bandwagon effect means that a lone marcher can quickly become thousands. And overconfidence bias warns leaders against assuming that outrage can be managed from above. The Nepali government ignored all of these lessons

and paid the price. It is almost comic in its irony, except for the fact that governments collapsed, economies suffered, and futures were derailed. The unrest in Nepal reminded the world that ignoring citizens' frustrations is a dangerous pastime.

Human beings are wired to get emotional, to follow the herd, and to react fiercely when their freedoms are restricted. Corruption combined with censorship does not suppress protest; it fuels it.

The next time a government believes that banning social media is a quick fix, it should take a behavioural nudge instead: listen to the people, understand their grievances, and focus on fixing the economy before fixing Facebook.

As Kahneman once put it, "We are blind to our blindness." Nepal's revolution was proof that when leaders fail to see, the people eventually make them look.

About the author

The author is MSS student at the Department of Economics in University of Dhaka

Beijing's Grand Stage: SCO summit and victory parade as a vision of a new world

By Shakil Khan and Tasnuva Tanzum

Military parade for V-day celebration, Beijing, China. Source: Kong Lingyang/Xinhua

On a clear September morning in 2025, Beijing, the capital of China, turned into a global theatre of power and diplomacy. After millennia of existence, the city now finds itself at a turning point in the swiftly shifting geopolitical landscape. The Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) summit and the Victory Day parade celebrating 80 years since Japan's defeat in the Second World War were not mere events but carefully curated narratives of China's vision for a new world, a vision that seeks to reshape the global order.

Beijing's showcase

The 25th annual Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) summit was held in Tianjin, China, at a time when the world has been thrown into turmoil by the United States' trade policies and tariffs, following

President Trump's return to office for a second term. It brought together leaders from across Eurasia, including Russia, India, Pakistan, Iran and other Central Asian nations. This was not just a routine diplomatic union but a declaration of intended vision.

The two-day event illustrated perfectly China's desire for regional economic dominance in order to counter the United States-led global trade system. Under Xi Jinping's leadership, the SCO has transformed from a regional security platform into a stage for shaping new geopolitical architecture. Xi articulated a vision that emphasised mutual respect and collective development in the East. His message was clear: establish a world where power is not monopolised but shared. Beijing hosted two major events in

a single week. Alongside the SCO summit, the city also witnessed the 80th Victory Day celebration parade in Tiananmen Square. China sought to cast itself as the leader of a multipolar world led by the Global South. The participation of leaders from Russia, Iran and India underscored the significance of the summit. Their presence highlighted the rising number of countries seeking alternatives to the US-led trade system.

The main topic of discussion was energy alliances and infrastructure development through initiatives like the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), positioning the SCO as a counterbalance to NATO and other Western alliances. It demonstrated China's strategic plan of mixing economic diplomacy with hard power. Xi Jinping presented a vision of global governance that prioritised shared development while subtly asserting China's leadership role. One of the most vital participants was India's Prime Minister Narendra Modi. His attendance drew considerable attention from Western leaders, particularly the United States, as it came after Trump imposed a 50% tariff on Indian products. Beijing, however, undoubtedly viewed the SCO summit as a powerful platform to present its vision of global relations.

Victory Parade: Power on display

Beijing's Victory Day parade offered a visual dynamic to the diplomatic world. It included cutting-edge weaponry such as hypersonic missiles and advanced drone systems, signalling China's advancement in next-generation military technology. Beyond the traditional display of tanks, missiles and troops, the parade was a statement of China's confidence in defending its interests. Marking the 80th anniversary of the end of the Second World War, the event was both

a grand show of military might and an expression of national pride. Beijing framed its ascent as a continuation of its historical responsibility to restore national dignity and international respect, commemorating its wartime sacrifices.

Until now, the global narrative of the Second World War has largely focused on the contributions of the United States, Soviet Union and Europe. The parade provided China with an opportunity to highlight its own historical role as well as its present-day strength. The parade also showcased the unity of China's allies. Russian and North Korean troops marching together symbolised shared interests in building a multipolar world. The absence of Western leaders, contrasted with the presence of figures such as Vladimir Putin and Kim Jong Un at both events, sparked significant concern in the West. Russia, meanwhile, continues to deepen its economic alliance with China. Its economy has been teetering on the brink of recession under US sanctions following its invasion of Ukraine in 2022. Ahead of his visit to China, Russian President Vladimir Putin openly opposed Western sanctions. As Western nations cut ties with Russia, China stepped in by importing Russian oil and electronics, underscoring their growing partnership.

A vision of a new world order

The SCO summit and Victory Day parade encapsulated Beijing's vision for a new world order, one where power is not concentrated in the West. They conveyed the message that the era of Western dominance is giving way to a more complex and multipolar world in which China plays a crucial role. China has consistently promoted the principle of non-interference in other nations' internal affairs, a stance that appeals to many developing countries wary of Western interventions.

The SCO's focus on cyber security, counter-terrorism and military collaboration reflects a collective approach to regional stability, with China positioning itself as the guarantor of security.

By blending contemporary events with historical milestones such as Victory Day, Beijing projects resilient leadership designed to appeal to international legitimacy. Together, the summit and parade sent a clear message: China is ready for a new era.

This vision challenges the post-Second World War order shaped by the United States and its Western allies, instead proposing a system where emerging powers have decisive voices.

The expansion of the SCO indicates a shift in global alliances, while the military parade demonstrated that this vision is backed by hard power. For China, it is not only about asserting power but also about shaping a world order that reflects its interests and values.

Technological ambitions

Economic cooperation was a vital part of the SCO discussions. China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), often referred to as the 21st-century Silk Road, featured prominently.

The summit highlighted new infrastructure projects, energy pipelines and digital connectivity plans designed to integrate the vast Eurasian landmass both economically and technologically. China's push for technological leadership also came into focus. Delegates discussed joint research in artificial intelligence, 5G and space exploration. These initiatives show that Beijing recognises future global influence will be shaped not only by military might but also by economic resilience and technological innovation.

Obstacles and challenges

Yet Beijing's vision is not without hurdles. The SCO faces internal diversity, bringing together nations with conflicting interests and rivalries. The India–Pakistan dispute, for instance, complicates attempts at unified action.

Moreover, member states worry that excessive reliance on China could create new vulnerabilities tied to its economic dominance. In the West, Beijing's vision is viewed with scepticism and concern. The Victory Day parade, in particular, was perceived as a provocative display in the midst of current geopolitical tensions. China, however, did not hesitate to send a strong message against the Western-led global order.

Looking Ahead: Beijing's prospects for future
In the heart of Beijing, past and present converged to signal a transformative moment in international relations. The world witnessed China stepping onto the global stage not as a marginal challenger but as a powerful visionary seeking to shape the future of international politics.

Beijing envisions a future of harmony between nations, between environments and cities, and between innovation for the future and preservation of history. By organising events such as the SCO summit and the Victory Day parade, it aims to reinforce its role as a hub for global dialogue. Proud of its history and confident in its current position, Beijing is determined to remain at the centre of international relations. Rooted in its historical legacy and driven by present aspirations, Beijing has embraced a foresight that seeks to define the future of Asia and, indeed, the wider world.

A desk with a lamp, stacks of papers, and several coffee cups.

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The day **Theodosian Walls** fell: Constantinople's collapse and birth of a new world

by Rakibul Amin

The Fall of Constantinople in 1453 was not just the end of the Byzantine Empire—it was a monumental turning point in global history. This single event reshaped trade, triggered a desperate search for alternative routes to the East, and arguably paved the way for the Age of Exploration.

For centuries, Constantinople had been more than a city; it was a strategic link between Europe and Asia, a vibrant hub where goods, cultures, and ideas converged. Its fall sent ripples across continents, altering the course of commerce, power, and discovery.

Strategically perched on the Bosphorus Strait, Constantinople was one of the most vital trade hubs in the pre-modern world. As the capital of the Byzantine Empire, the city stood at the crossroads of Europe and Asia, controlling crucial land and sea routes that connected the East to the West.

This unique position made Constantinople a gateway for the Silk Road, where caravans from China, India, and Persia would feed into European markets. From spices and silk to porcelain and pre-

cious stones, Eastern luxuries were exchanged here for European goods such as wool, silver, and gold. The city's thriving ports turned it into a melting pot of commerce, culture, and religion. Italian maritime powers—especially Venice and Genoa—recognised its value early, establishing their own trading quarters in the city.

These merchants became key distributors of Eastern products across Europe, making Constantinople the heartbeat of medieval international trade. Even after the city fell to the Ottomans in 1453, it remained an economic powerhouse under the name Istanbul. The Ottomans maintained their position as a commercial hub, thereby further solidifying their place in global economic history.

Constantinople's enduring influence, rooted in geography and sustained by empires, illustrates how a single city can shape the movement of goods, ideas, and power across the world.

Ottoman conquest and trade disruption

The conquest of Constantinople by Sultan Mehmed II, also known as Mehmed the Conqueror, marked a significant turning point in history. On May 29, 1453, after a 55-day siege, the Ottomans breached the city's ancient land walls, leading to the fall of the Byzantine Empire.

Mehmed II surrounded Constantinople by land and sea, using cannons to bombard its formidable defences. Mehmed surrounded the city by both land and sea, breaking through what was once considered impenetrable.

As the Ottoman Empire took control of Constantinople, it gained command over key land routes that connected Europe with Asia. This control allowed the Ottomans to influence and sometimes restrict the flow of goods, particularly affecting the trade of spices and other valuable commodities that were traditionally transported through these routes. The Ottomans' control of key trade routes significantly impacted European economies during the late medieval and early modern periods.

Overall, the control of trade routes played a crucial role in shaping European economic strategies and contributed to the broader geopolitical shifts that characterised the early modern period.

Alternative Trade Routes

In response to the Ottoman control of Constantinople and the surrounding region, European powers began to explore new maritime routes to access the riches of Asia directly, bypassing the overland routes that were now under Ottoman influence. This quest for alternative routes was a significant factor in the Age of Exploration. Notably, the Portuguese, under the sponsorship of Prince Henry the Navigator, embarked on voyages along the west coast of Africa, eventually discovering the sea route to India around the Cape of Good Hope by the end of the 15th century. The Spanish, motivated by similar desires to access Asian markets, sponsored Christopher Columbus's voyages, which led to the discovery of the Americas in 1492. These explorations not only opened new trade routes but also marked the beginning of European colonial expansion.

Portugal, under the visionary leadership of Prince Henry the Navigator, concentrated on exploring the west coast of Africa. Their goal was to discover a sea route to the spice-rich regions of Asia by navigating around the African continent. These efforts bore fruit when Bartolomeu Dias rounded the Cape of Good Hope in 1488, and Vasco da Gama successfully reached India in 1498, establishing direct maritime trade links with Asia.

Despite these developments, Venice initially continued to dominate the Oriental trade through its stronghold over Mediterranean routes in cooperation with Egypt. Venetian merchants maintained a near-monopoly on the distribution of Eastern luxury goods—especially spices—across Europe. However, the Portuguese discovery of a viable sea route to Asia through the Cape of Good Hope gradually undermined Venice's dominance and marked the beginning of a new era in global trade. In today's world, the strategic importance of trade routes remains just as strong. The opening of the Suez Canal in 1869 revived the Mediterranean as a crucial trade passage, once again connecting Europe with Asia—similar to Constantinople's role in the past. Modern trade hubs like Turkey, which links Europe and Asia, reflect the Ottoman Empire's former role as a global connector. Additionally, Mehmed II's multicultural and inclusive approach to rebuilding Constantinople mirrors the nature of today's global cities, which thrive on diversity and international commerce.

Microbial biofactories and sustainable agriculture

By Madhurja M. Rumalee

Illustration: Mahdi/Econology

Did you know that around 8–15 tonnes of microorganisms exist in soil? According to research by Ohio State University, it was found that soil contains 19.63% bacteria, 19.63% actinomycetes, 58.15% fungi, and the rest, 2.59%, contributes to algae, protozoa, and nematodes. Millions of these microorganisms, which we are referring to as “microbial biofactories” in this article, bring about environmental sustainability, efficient nutrient use, increased growth, and pest and phytopathogen resistance to their host crop.

Indeed, soil health plays a crucial role in cultivating more food, fuel, and fibre for the growing world population. Traditionally, to meet the growing demand, the industrialisation of agriculture led to farmers using excessive amounts of fertilisers and

pesticides. This, in turn, caused harm to the environment, including air, water, and soil pollution—species of bees, fish, and plants became extinct, resulting in a fractured ecosystem—and also posed a threat to soil biodiversity, i.e., changes in porosity, texture, and permeability.

From an economic perspective, supply chain experts and environmental researchers consider traditional farming practices to be “not healthy”. Natural resources are limited, and overusing them for global food needs seems questionable. Not only does this practice cause pollution, but it is not sustainable in the long run. So what if we could grow more crops with fewer resources, but cause less impact on the environment? How? Sustainable agriculture! Microbial communities have made sustainable

agriculture possible by bringing forward innovations in cultivating crops, controlling pests, maintaining soil health, securing global food, and ensuring environmental safety.

Molecular technologies, like genetically modifying organisms, recycling nutrients, precision farming, and making microbial fertilisers, use microorganisms, like bacteria, fungi, protozoa, and other species. What is truly environmentally sustainable agriculture? Well, sustainable agriculture is beyond just a concept; it is a process. This type of agriculture employs precise farming techniques that utilise environmental resources without causing harm to them.

One of the major resources that gets used up for agricultural purposes is space. According to Urban Ecosystems, research conducted in 2015 showed that most of the agricultural land was occupied by recreational spots.

This figure illustrates the average percentage distribution of land used among various categories of agricultural crops. With increasing population and housing, modern innovation comes up with two precise sustainable farming methods that save up space and produce more crops:

Urban farming is regarded as sustainable because it makes use of spaces such as rooftops, balconies, and greenhouses, which are increasingly important in light of rapid urbanisation and the growing demand for food. This form of agriculture supports local and sustainable food systems, contributing positively to the climate, ecosystem, and environment. Additionally, urban farming promotes community cohesion and enhances the health of residents. Cultivating in fields and greenhouses occupies space, but vertical farming techniques have come up with a

unique method where crops are grown on top of each other in a tower to harvest more in less space.

Integration of microbes, sustainable agriculture

These sustainable agriculture methods use “microbial biofactories” in maintaining soil, plant, and environmental health. These microbial biofactories exist in a nutrient-rich region directly in contact with the plants’ roots, known as the rhizosphere.

It is a diverse and complex ecosystem of bacteria, fungi, protozoa, and other microbes. Although most microbial actions occur naturally, effective inoculations involving specific microbes can enhance crop diversity, promote plant growth, and improve agro-climatic conditions.

A certain bacterium known as *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* is the most used microbe in molecular technology for plant transformation. Well, how it works is a more complex process and requires another article to explain, but in short, it is used to introduce new genes to a plant’s DNA to create a desirable gene product.

Bacillus thuringiensis (Bt) is a type of bacteria that acts as a natural pesticide and works very well against pests like the corn borer, tobacco budworm, potato beetle, and cotton bollworm, helping to create Bt-protected crops like corn, tobacco, cotton, and potatoes. Nitrogen-fixing bacteria, like the *Azotobacter* and *Rhizobium*, do not directly provide nutrients to the plants but provide support in accessing the nutrients. These bacteria help in converting atmospheric nitrogen to ammonium, which is vital for plant survival. In sustainable agriculture, Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi, or AMF,

are one of the most well-known microbial biostimulants and play a significant part in producing better, healthier, and more useful crops.

They help crops absorb water and nutrients, improve their ability to withstand drought and salinity, and lessen soil erosion. Additionally, *Trichoderma* has shown that it can effectively recycle nutrients by releasing substances that help seeds grow and enzymes that break down plant materials, especially in organic tea and greenhouse farming. Not to forget, the major component of biofertilizers is fungi, which boost nutrient availability through their biological activity.

The microbial biofactory is a whole ecosystem in itself. Protozoa help in maintaining the overall microbial population in the rhizosphere; they feed on pathogenic bacteria to release nitrogen, in turn promoting plant health. The interaction between protozoa and bacteria results in the production of plant growth hormones, known as auxins. This process enhances overall root development and plant growth. A notable fact about protozoa is that they serve as scientific markers because of their sensitivity to soil pH, moisture, and pollution. Hence, their presence allows farmers to understand soil fertility and minimise waste for more sustainable farming methods.

Other microbes are not directly associated with plant health but enhance soil quality. These include: Actinomycetes like *Streptomyces* spp, which work as soil conditioners to break down complex organic materials, such as chitin and cellulose. Cyanobacteria, also known as blue-green algae, work as biofertilizers in paddy fields and waterlogged soils, Algae enhances the microbial biofactories. Viruses like baculoviruses are used as bioinsecticides

against specific pests.

Economic, and environmental benefits

According to the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), sustainable agriculture is such a technology in farming that provides environmentally friendly products like food and fibre.

It ensures the well-being of humans, the welfare of animals, and the health of all species on Earth. Sociological, economic, and ecological scholars believe that this method can be adapted to reduce the effect of climate change, lessen the greenhouse effect, retain the health of ecosystems, stop the loss of biodiversity, and produce sufficient safe and nutrient-rich food.

The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) asserts that sustainable agriculture promotes food safety and nutrition while also protecting social, cultural, and environmental ethics. Developments in sustainable agriculture will depend primarily on research focused on development, optimising, and understanding the interactions between the environment and microbes.

About Author

Madhurja Mahrab Rumalee earned her BSc in Biotechnology from UCSI University in Malaysia. She promotes sustainable event management, and her environmental activism is driven by her academic background.

A photograph of a desk at night, illuminated by a warm lamp. The desk is cluttered with stacks of papers, several coffee cups in various colors (red, white, orange, green, blue), a pen holder with pens, and a glass jar. The background is dark and out of focus, showing a window with blinds.

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Rewriting the sustainability narrative

Marla Lise

Sustainability took off like a bat out of hell. In just a few years, it became the silver bullet solution to our environmental woes. “ESG” (Environmental, Social, Governance) was on everyone’s lips.

Universities raced to offer new degrees. Companies hired Chief Sustainability Officers and released bold net-zero statements. The scramble to get the sustainability industry established, however, has been just that.

A scramble. A closer look reveals a troubling reality: sustainability has become more of a branding exercise, almost a fad, than a transformative force. We are now left with an urgent question: what happened to sustainability, and how can we rewrite its narrative so it becomes more than a corporate checkbox?

The great sustainability scramble

The race to establish sustainability as a central pillar of business and governance has been, quite frankly, chaotic. Many companies scrambled to position themselves as leaders in sustainability, often with little understanding of what true sustainability entails.

Grand promises were made: carbon neutrality by 2030, 2040, or 2050, fully recycled packaging, or perfect ESG scores. Yet, according to a 2023 study in *Nature Climate Change*, of the 1,041 firms that had set emissions targets ending in 2020, 88 outright failed, and 320 simply disappeared from reporting. That’s nearly 40% of firms vanishing from the very game they helped set in motion. This leads us to an essential question: who is holding whom accountable?

And more importantly, what kind of story have we been telling ourselves, and each other, about what sustainability really means?

Language trap: Carbon and tunnel vision

In today's sustainability narrative, carbon has taken centre stage. Conversations around ESG often reduce down to carbon emissions, carbon offsets, and carbon credits. Scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions dominate the agenda. Carbon literacy certifications are used as a benchmark for progress. But this narrow focus has created what some now call "carbon tunnel vision."

We've mistaken the part for the whole. Carbon accounting is just one small piece of the sustainability puzzle, important, yes, but insufficient in addressing the deeper ecological and social challenges we face. By obsessing over carbon, we risk ignoring the more uncomfortable truths: our addiction to growth, the exploitation of people and ecosystems, the loss of biodiversity, and the erosion of meaning in our modern lives. Carbon has become the scapegoat for a much bigger, systemic malaise. It offers the illusion of progress while keeping business-as-usual comfortably intact.

Rise and stall of corporate sustainability

Over the last two years, corporate interest in sustainability has begun to wane. The initial rush is giving way to hesitation and fatigue. In 2024, Eco-Business published an article that economic uncertainty had "emboldened companies and governments to justify slowing climate action." The Straits Times echoed this sentiment, revealing that "over half of Singapore CEOs have pushed sustainability down their to-do list." Why? Because real sustainability is hard. It's expensive. It forces businesses to confront

uncomfortable trade-offs and change long-standing practices. And without genuine public pressure or regulatory enforcement, there is little incentive to go beyond what looks good on paper.

Carbon as villain

Another unintended consequence of the current narrative is the vilification of carbon itself - an element essential to life. Humans are carbon-based beings. So are plants, animals, and the entire biosphere. Yet we now talk about carbon as if it were a toxin to be buried underground, stored in machines, or blasted into space.

This language matters. By framing carbon as the enemy, we risk forgetting the real culprit: our systems of extraction, exploitation, and unchecked growth. We are trying to remove the symptoms while ignoring the cause.

Challenging the current narrative

Language shapes perception, and perception drives behaviour. If we want sustainability to be meaningful again, we need a new narrative. One that moves beyond carbon metrics and ESG scorecards. One that is grounded in connection, care, and systemic thinking. It may be time to acknowledge that sustainability, as we know it, has had its moment. It succeeded in starting the conversation, but now it's time to move forward. The world needs more than sustainability. It needs regeneration.

Rewriting narrative: From sustainability to regeneration

Regeneration is a fundamentally different approach. Where sustainability focuses on minimising harm while functioning as usual, regeneration focuses on restoring

health of people, ecosystems, and culture. Regenerative systems place purpose over profit, well-being over efficiency, and relationships over transactions. They are rooted in reciprocity, guided by place-based knowledge, and informed by indigenous wisdom and ecological science.

They view wealth holistically - encompassing not just financial capital, but social, cultural, and spiritual capital as well. More importantly, regeneration reframes our role. No longer are we consumers trying to reduce our footprint. We become co-creators, healers, and stewards. We should no longer ask, "How can we do less harm?" Instead, we must ask, "How can we do more good?"

Language as a tool

To rewrite the sustainability narrative, we must start with our words. The language we use shapes the frameworks we operate within. It influences our policies, our business models, our metrics of success - and our imaginations.

The way we speak about our planet, our work, and our lives essentially frames how we treat it. So, we have to shift the language we're using - no more sustainability jargon, only restorative regenerative concepts: net-zero to net-positive, carbon offsets, ecological restoration, sustainability reporting to impactful storytelling. Regeneration puts people and planet first, and replaces profit with purpose.

It looks at restoring and healing rather than extracting and exploiting. It's time to shift the narrative from reducing emissions to repairing soil, restoring forests, reviving communities, and reweaving our relationship with the natural world. It's not about asking, "How can we continue with business as

usual?" It's time instead to ask, "How can we give back? Restore? Heal?"

Reimagination

The old sustainability narrative, with its checklists and carbon counts, was never enough to address the complexity of our global crisis. It was a necessary beginning - but it cannot carry us forward. To meet the moment we're in, we need a deeper, bolder, more human story. One that recognises the interdependence of all life. One that values healing as much as efficiency. One that honours the Earth as a living system, not just a resource bank. Every meaningful change begins inside: with the courage to ask who you are, what brings you joy, and what you believe in. This is the work of reeducation: learning to hear your voice again and learning about the reality of the world around us. When your inner world aligns with your values, you begin to live and act with integrity.

That's regeneration in motion - starting with yourself, regenerating more mindful ways of living. And when your story reflects your truth, you don't just speak - you reimagine what's possible for yourself and for others too. Reimagining better future narratives. A better future can exist in a better vocabulary, because stories shape systems, and language can lead to transformation.

About the writer:

Marla Lise is an earthling, weaving her love for stories, dreams, and adventure into a mission to protect the planet - regenerating, reeducating, and reimagining for a better future. She does this through her company, The Eco Chapter. Come use words towards change@theecochapter.

Smocha Dilemma: How behavioural economics explains our cravings

*Dr Christine Nyakerario . Pharmacist
Nairobi, Kenya*

Illustration: Mahdi/Econology/

It's 21 hours in Nairobi. A young man has just left work. A gruelling and exhausting day. He thinks of how he still needs to beat traffic. The thought of cooking a meal from scratch just feels harrowing. The man just wants a quick meal, a shower, and rest. Mama Osano's smochas – chapatis rolled in sausages - feel like heaven. Quick. Simple. Easy. He will get one, or maybe two. Over the past few years, there have been many educational campaigns on healthy eating. Nevertheless, many Kenyans still choose to eat fast/ junk food.

A study by the Ministry of Health in Kenya indicates that almost 50% of hospital admissions in the country are due to

non-communicable diseases related to diet. Why, then, does behaviour change proportionally to these findings? People do not make decisions haphazardly. They make them under influence, subconsciously or consciously. People make decisions based on convenience over care. This article digs deep into the behavioural forces, i.e, “nudges” that push people to unhealthy food despite their intention of consuming healthy food, and what can be done to counter the former popular but dangerous narrative.

Is it easy to choose now over later?

There's a propensity to lean into instant gratification over lasting rewards – present bias. Fast food offers the former, tantalising

the senses, while healthy food comes with planning, more preparation time, and a higher initial cost. On a Monday morning, a bus conductor will grab a fizzy drink – a soda and a mandazi, unassumingly – unaware that he is putting his health at risk. His priority at that moment is to get something in his stomach – anything that is quick and filling – through the next few hours. He couldn't care less about what this habit would do to his body in a few years.

Behaviour change is brought about by reframing. We need to show people that healthy choices made now are wins. Like how whole meal grains, when eaten in the morning, fuel you longer throughout the day, or how sweet snacks make you feel tired and sluggish by mid-morning.

How does choice architecture fit into this?

We mostly make choices according to what's convenient. What we can access fastest, with the least effort. This is where choice architecture comes in. The way choice is presented in our environment, in this case, what food is accessible in our environment and how it is presented in those environments.

In most, if not all, cases, food's choice architecture goes against good health.

An example is my city, Nairobi. Most food vendors are on the street, selling fried salty and sweet snacks.

You would have to travel further and wait longer, as well as pay more to get healthier choices. This is an example of the "default effect," meaning that people tend to choose what they see or is right in front of them, even if it's the worst choice. The solution would be to place more fruit stalls in popular/frequented areas like bus stops. This avails a better option to be chosen, meaning some, if

not all, may choose that option just because it is availed. When we run out of 'damns' to give, we make many decisions in a day. What to wear, what commute route to take that day, and the tasks to start with. We are always making decisions, and at the end of the day, we become fatigued.

Deciding on what to eat seems small, inconsequential. Come on, we are busy deciding on how to grow our businesses, who to hire, what to invest in, so choosing what to eat takes the back burner. We consider it a minute detail.

Except it is not. Research shows that the more stressed and tired a population is, the more high-fat, high-calorie foods it takes in. It's the dopamine that kicks in after taking these foods that counters the stress we are experiencing, that pushes us to these foods.

Cooking in batches and hiring affordable help to prepare meals helps reduce the decision fatigue that pushes us to not-so-wise decisions.

Do we feel that influences what we eat

Food not only nourishes us, it also moves us emotionally. In behavioural economics, this is known as a "heuristic effect," where the way we feel influences our choices more than what we know is right.

A young person, after a stressful day of work, would rather eat a sweet or salty, unhealthy snack to numb the stress they are feeling.

Fast food joints in malls on Sunday afternoons in Nairobi are usually filled with many parents who go to buy their children some fast food, as a reward or even probably a break from what they eat during the week, what many call a Sunday after church treat.

What other people eating?

Peer pressure will never die. It's psychological. It's human. You eat what others around you are eating. Again – convenience. Also, we want a sense of belonging. In Kenya, a meal of ugali and sukumawiki is considered food for the have-nots. This is because that meal combination is considered basic, almost every household has access to it, while junk food like French fries and chicken is considered food for the haves since fast food joints like KFC are found in urban centres and are a bit pricier.

A solution would be changing this narrative. Educating the masses, from schools to marketplaces to malls, we need to change how people think about food.

Scarcity changes how people think about food. There's not enough time, money, or mental bandwidth. So what do many people do? They chose the cheapest foods, most filling, high-calorie per shilling, because of this, fresh and healthy foods are found inadequate.

What may help is placing many subsidies on healthier options – fruits and vegetables, incentivising street food vendors so that they stock healthy options, and bringing up community kitchens. Making healthy food - a default option.

Path of least resistance

People do not make unhealthy choices of food because they lack knowledge or drive. This is backward thinking. Behavioural economics points us to the truth – that most decisions are not rational, they are shaped and influenced by our environment, by subtle cues.

We don't just need to know better, we need to influence better - “nudge” better. Make healthy food easier to find, more affordable, and more accessible.

Author Bio

Christine Nyakerario is a licensed pharmacist based in Nairobi, Kenya, passionate about health communication and health advocacy. She is keen on exploring behavioural science, policy, and storytelling in the healthcare field. She uses her pharmacy practice experience to dive into the psychology behind people's decision-making and seeks to find better ways to support better decision-making.

